

THESIS EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

IMPACT OF INCOME INEQUALITY ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN MOROCCO

EVALUATION USING A MICRO-MACRO ANALYSIS (CGE MODEL)

Abstract -

Although the world has experienced increased affluence, disparities among its inhabitants have continued to rise, reshaping our understanding of the concept of "poverty". This executive summary of my thesis dissertation presents a condensed version of a comprehensive theoretical and empirical inquiry into the socioeconomic ramifications of income inequality on the stability of a developing economy, specifically the Moroccan economy. The theoretical segment of this research involves an exploration of the underlying theories surrounding income inequality in order to conceptualize its influence on economic advancement. The empirical component is bifurcated into two distinct phases, an exploratory phase and a modeling phase. The former stage is concerned with assessing the dynamic nature of inequality in Morocco and identifying the factors contributing to its growth. The latter phase employs a static ECG model, calibrated on Moroccan SAM 2016, to simulate multiple scenarios in order to scrutinize the socioeconomic impacts of a mere 1% increase in income inequality. Our results reveal that a 1% increase in inequality precipitates a 1.73% decline in GDP.

Keywords

Income inequality, socioeconomic impact, developing economy, fiscal policy, CGE model.

JEL CODE

C68, D63, E62, H31

Note:

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**The Socio-Economic Impact of Income Inequality:
Evaluation using a Computable General Equilibrium
Model (CGE) for the case of Morocco**

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- May their souls rest in eternal peace -

Introduction

“The political problem of mankind consists in combining three things: economic efficiency, social justice and political freedom.”

John Maynard KEYNES, (1936)

Extract from the book, *General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money*

The world is made of inequalities. In all human societies and ideologies, there has long been an important debate on the nature of the relationship between development and socio-economic inequalities (Piketty, 2021). From a purely monetary perspective, inequalities can be distinguished into two categories: wealth inequalities and income inequalities. The wealth of an individual or household represents its stock of assets (movable or immovable property) minus its liabilities (debt and loans). It represents the buildings, financial investments and other valuable properties that make up one's wealth. While income is the flow of available resources that fuels one's consumption and savings (Hicks, 1948). Given the extent and complexity of the subject, our thesis will be limited to the treatment of income inequality. Therefore, when we refer to income inequality, we are referring to the way in which new resources are distributed.

A divided society risks compromising its prosperity (Stiglitz, 2012). After the collapse of the financial markets in 2008, the issue of inequality has never been more topical. Many authors, including Nobel laureates in economics, have expressed concern about the scale of the phenomenon (Deaton A. (2015); Sen A. (2011; 2012); Stiglitz J. (2012, 2015) and Krugman P. (2008)). All these publications share a common view that reveals some correlation between rising inequality and slower economic growth in developed countries. This reinforces the hypothesis that inequality is a drag on growth. This hypothesis has been widely defended in many articles (Bourguignon, 2015; Ostry et al., 2014, Nissanke and Thorbecke, 2006; Banerjee and Duflo, 2003; Benhabib, 2003; Thorbecke and Charumilind, 2002; Aghion et al.).

According to the recent World Inequality Report, this phenomenon appears to be global and irreversible (Alvaredo, 2018). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which define the optimal way to address the challenges facing the world, consider the reduction of inequality as central to achieving the desired progress. However, addressing inequality requires policies that are specific to the concerned countries. Therefore, the aim of our research is to measure the potential impact of an increase in income inequality on a national economy, in this case the Moroccan economy.

In Morocco, income inequality is far from extreme, but it is still quite worrying. From 1984 to 2016, the income share of the wealthiest 10% is estimated at almost 47-49% of Moroccan national income (WID, 2020). Although this portion appears to be high, it remains below the level recorded in highly unequal countries such as in Sub-Saharan Africa and the Middle East. Morocco has made gains in the fight against absolute poverty through a series of social programs. Per capita consumption has risen significantly since 1991, from \$800 to \$1200 in 2014. Yet the rapid growth in income remains a privilege for the top of the hierarchy, namely the wealthiest 0.01%, who have an income almost 20 times higher than the average income of the top decile.

In the past decade, social inequality in Morocco has reached a turning point. Since 2016, many institutional reports have addressed the issue (HCP, DEPF, CESE, ONDH...). This desire for inclusion is present even in the highest political sphere of the kingdom, where HM King Mohammed VI acknowledged the alarming increase in inequalities in his 2019 Throne Day speech. From now on, the fight against inequalities is presented as a fundamental principle in the elaboration of the new Moroccan development model.

Research problematic

Rising socio-economic inequality is a phenomenon of multiple proportions. Marked by a global, excessive and irreversible increase, the causes and consequences of this phenomenon transcend purely economic factors. Given such conceptual complexities, a problematical issue arises regarding

the dynamics of the existing inequalities and the nature of their impact. This problem is expressed in the following central question:

What socio-economic impact does income inequality exert on the Moroccan economy?

Aiming at providing answers to this issue, our approach targets two major objectives:

- **1st research objective:** Determine the causes and multidimensional consequences of economic inequalities on the conceptual, theoretical and empirical level (relative to the case of Morocco). This will make it possible to identify the impact that the development of this phenomenon has on the socio-economic foundations that guarantee the stability of the macroeconomic balance. The aim is to take a position on the fact that economic inequalities might express a form of social injustice. Furthermore, to show that they generate a cost on economic development and social prosperity as a whole.

- **2nd research objective:** To measure the impact of increasing inequality on the stability of the macroeconomic and social balance of a national economy, in this case Morocco. Using an ex-ante modelling approach, we aim to identify the transmission channels of this impact and identify the effects on certain aggregates (growth, employment, return on capital, accessibility of the poor and rural people to basic products, etc.).

Research hypothesis

Inequality and its determinants of socio-economic impact are either positively or negatively correlated, or have a non-linear relationship, or are otherwise uncorrelated. In line with this reasoning, we adapted the research hypotheses to the central question of our study :

- H_1 : Income inequality has a positive effect on Moroccan socioeconomic development
- H_2 : Income inequalities have a negative impact on socioeconomic development in Morocco
- H_3 : Income inequality and socioeconomic development have a non-linear relationship
- H_4 : Income inequality has no effect on socio-economic development in Morocco

Document structure

In the long version, our thesis is structured in a binary plan divided into two main parts. The first part is theoretical. It includes two chapters, the first of which deals with the conceptual fields of the two notions "inequality" and "income". The second chapter presents a literature review on the economic, social and societal determinants of income inequality. The second part is empirical. It deals in its first chapter with the dynamics of income inequality in Morocco. The second and last chapter of the thesis is dedicated to the presentation of the CGE modelling issues and the results of the simulated scenarios.

In this short version, we focus only on the key contributions of our research work. Thus, apart from the introduction and conclusion, this document is divided into three parts: Theoretical and empirical context, methodology and results.

The first is divided into two: theoretical and empirical context. The theoretical part focuses on the perception of inequality in economic thought since the classical school, a review of the literature on the nature of the relationship between inequality and economic development and a conceptualization of the impact of inequality in general equilibrium. The empirical part is an exploratory analysis of data on the dynamics of income inequality in Morocco. This analysis allows to raise the determinants of the growth of inequalities specific to Morocco.

The methodology part provides a patent overview of our research approach (reasoning path, epistemological positioning...) as well as the way in which our Ex-ante approach allows to integrate the simulation of inequalities into the standard CGEM.

The result section, as its name indicates, presents the main results obtained to quantify the impact of an increase (or decrease) in income inequality on the general economic equilibrium calibrated on data from Morocco in 2016. This part is accompanied by a discussion that confronts the results obtained with the established literature review.

In conclusion, we will cite the main implications developed as well as an evaluation of the research hypotheses. We also present the main limitations of our research as well as the prospects for further development of this study.

THEORETICAL CONTEXT

Revue on socioeconomic inequality impacts

Despite the increase in global trade and the information technology revolution, recent economic growth has been sluggish in the United States and Europe long before the repercussions of the global health crisis emerged. Without significant and easily identifiable factors, some authors have focused on the effects of non-market externalities. In considering this issue, we are interested in exploring the socioeconomic impact of rising inequalities. Our theoretical background is developed mainly to conceptualize and explain how these inequalities affect the flow of economic circulation. Nevertheless, we shall first outline the background to the acknowledgement of inequalities throughout the history of economic thought since the classical liberal school. Then, we will present a review of the literature that includes some of the most relevant studies established to understand the relationship between rising inequality and economic growth and development.

1- Theoretical background : Inequality origins in history of economic thought

Understanding the causes and consequences of inequality, mostly income inequality, is a much-debated question (Dabla-Norris et al, 2015 ; Neckerman & Torche, 2007; Banerjee & Duflo, 2003). Although the theoretical background of the evolution of socio-economic disparities is unclear, one particular theory manages to explain its causes. According to Piketty (2013), a major authority on the subject, if we distinguish income into two categories - labour income and capital income - we can see that they do not develop at the same rate. In a liberal pro-capitalist environment, the return on capital would always be higher than any form of improvement in income from wages alone, even in the case of a highly skilled executive. As a result, the wealth of capital owners grows faster, thus widening the gap between this minority and the rest of the population (Piketty, 2013). While this theory can pertinently explain the causes of the divergence in the evolution of income, what about the consequences? Or in other words, how has the increase in socio-economic inequality been perceived throughout the mainstream of economic thought?

Regarding the sharing of resources, the notion of equity is a thought that dates back to ancient Greece (Destrée, 1990). "Equity for all" is a moral value rooted in societal perception and beliefs, especially when maintaining social balance remains a sacred goal. Some experts believe that the reason why citizens revolt against their political systems is, above all, related to a sense of injustice (Sen, 2012; Stiglitz, 2015). Stiglitz (2013) states that society pays the price for the lack of equity that leads to entrenched structural income gaps. However, this idea has not been the object of consensus throughout the history of economic thought.

In a juxtaposition of thesis and anti-thesis, it is evident that the idea of inequality has changed its meaning over time and from one school of thought to another. In an optimistic or neutral perception, the increase in inequality, as a result of the concentration of earnings in the hands of a minority, is seen as a natural consequence based on the laws of merit and competition. Therefore, all forms of non-market redistribution are rejected. The liberal, neo-liberal and ultra-liberal schools of thought have all taken this view to some degree. By contrast, an opposite view puts the notion of equity at the center of the objectives of all economic development. This rather pessimistic perception calls for state intervention to remedy the dysfunction of markets. This philosophy was raised by Marx and later updated by Keynes and his successors. Without diving into details, the following panoramic overview distinguishes between authors who perceive inequalities in an optimistic perspective those who denounce them.

OPPOSITION TO CAPITALISM

IN FAVOUR OF MARKET LIBERALISATION

NEO-KEYNESIEN

The cost of inequality (mostly political/social instability) weighs heavily on economic performance (e.g., post-crisis riots in 2007)

STIGLITZ J.
US (1943-)

> Social justice is irrelevant cos sharing cannot occur outside the market
> All governmental social initiatives must be exercised either through negative taxation or through trickle-down

FREIDMAN M.
US (1912-2006)

POST-KEYNESIEN

> **KALDOR N. (1957)**: Inequalities are the driving force of economic growth through increasing national savings and strengthening investments (the virtuous circle theory)
> **KALECKI M. (1954)**: Inequalities are an inevitable consequence of the capitalist system; this thought is reinforced by Piketty's theory of divergence forces (2013).

Social inequalities cannot be resolved spontaneously on the markets without state intervention via budgetary investment, monetary stimulus and fiscal regulation policies

KEYNES J.M.
UK (1883-1946)

KUZNETS S.
USA (1901-1985)

> The first to study the impact of inequality on economic performance, confirms the positive effect of disparities on development through industrialization
> Inequality is therefore a temporary phase that results in convergence to common development (Kuznets curve)

SCHUMPETER J.
AT (1883-1950)

> Inequality is a natural consequence that distinguishes those who have benefited from progress by innovating from others. Thus, social justice is an illusion (Hayek, 1979)
> Any redistribution acts violates the principles of meritocracy, self-ownership and individual freedom (Nozick, 1974)

WALRAS L.
FR (1834-1910)

> In an unequal economy, individual failure is not always driven by his own actions
> The resolution of inequalities is a component in Walras' neoliberal reform of the economic system. This system reinforces the inclusion of wealth distribution bodies: Justice (duty of reciprocity), associations and charity
> The ultimate goal of an inclusive system is to preserve perfect equality of opportunity in Rawls' term (1987)

> Inequality is a form of injustice that reflects the exploitation of a superior class by the rest of the social classes (Social Stratification Theory)
> Rejects those inequalities are necessary for economic ascent
> Infinite accumulation of capital necessarily leads to a labour revolt

MARXISME

MARX K.
DE (1818-1883)

> Inequality prophesies the apocalypse by proving the incapacity of resources to satisfy everyone's needs (Malthusianism Chaos)
> Restructuring to avoid overpopulation, even abolishing aid to the poor

MALTHUS T.
UK (1766-1834)

RICARDO D.
UK (1772-1823)

> Income distribution is market-based, and inequalities remain for the benefit of all according to Smith's vision
> Aid laws for the poor and the rent economy must be abolished to free the economy.

SMITH A.
UK (1723-1790)

> Inequalities are integral to an efficient and profitable economy in modern, civilized society (need for luxury consumption)
> Distribution spontaneously exercised either out of duty, altruism or vanity.
> In Smith's model, workers are appropriately valued in the social hierarchy (co-dependence implies coexistence)

> Legitimacy of private property rights
> The just consists in a certain equality, but the reduction of inequalities is never an end in itself (Piketty, 2019)

ARISTOTE
GR (-386 / -322)

PESSIMISTIC PERCEPTION

OPTIMISTIC PERCEPTION

2 – Literature review of existing study on inequality and economic development¹

At the close of the Second World War, the primary challenge for Western countries has been to stimulate the economic apparatus in order to repair damage caused by the war. In both North America and Europe, the economic recovery had a positive impact on the social climate of their countries. This sense of social peace, indicated by the population explosion (Dumont, 2014), was reinforced by an inclusive economic development where inequalities maintained a very low level, perhaps the most egalitarian since the beginning of 18th century (Piketty, 2013).

After a decade of world peace, Kuznets (1955), an American economist and statistician mentioned earlier, proposed a hypothesis that links development to inequality illustrated by a curve called the 'Kuznets curve'. This hypothesis assumes that economic emergence would be inimical to social equity - reflected in greater economic inequality - during the first phase of development. Beyond a certain level of growth in per capita income, a generalized recovery in environmental quality leads to a smooth stabilization of inequality in the Gini sense. Second, any increase in growth - indicated by average per capita income - leads to a reduction in inequality.

This assumption was appreciated during the period of the thirty glorious years. Up to 1980, the empirical results of economic development, especially in the United States, corresponded rather well to Kuznets' prophecy (Greenwood & Jovanovic, 1990). Once the social repercussions of the 1973 oil shock were felt, this idea that the dynamics of private capital accumulation should be systematically accompanied by balancing forces was no longer valid. What was missing from Kuznets' hypothesis was that capital accumulation was not necessarily accompanied by an increase in demand. At the same time as Kuznets' work, Kalecki's (1954) macroeconomics, a post-Keynesian economist, proves that owners of capital earn what they spend, while wage earners spend what they earn. In the absence of an efficient distribution mechanism, capitalists can only increase and protect their returns on investment (Piketty, 2020; Stiglitz, 2015).

Several economists have recently argued that the hyper-capitalist model is not only the source of the inequality trap but also responsible for the lack of growth (OECD, 2014; Garcia-Penalosa, 2017; Banerjee and Duflo, 2003; Bourguignon, 2015). In absolute terms, can we consider inequality as a brake or a driver of growth and development, or does it have a mixed effect? Given the complexity of the inequality-growth nexus, the issue of distribution is now one of the most contentious and debated. In the following section, we will summarize the existing literature on the relationship between income inequality and economic development and growth in four aspects:

■ Positive impact of inequality on economic development :

Although he is of the post-Keynesian school, Kaldor (1955) argues that inequality allows savings to increase. In a virtuous circle, the concentration of capital in a minority serves to sustain investment resulting in growth. Inequality is described by Okun (1975) as a natural force that acts as a stimulant to economic performance. Similarly, it helps to generate a general incentive for innovation and entrepreneurship in the hope of enrichment (Lazear and Rosen, 1981). Bhattacharya (1998) assesses

¹ It is important to note that in the longer version of the thesis, we have explored a link between inequality and all of these determinants raised by the scientific community. These determinants assess three levels of impact, namely: (i) Economic impact determined by the four fundamental markets (commodity production market, labour market, financial market and market openness); (ii) Social impact determined by education, health and welfare; (iii) Societal impact composed of determinants that guarantee more stability and cohesion, namely: social capital according to Bourdieu, lower crime rates, social involvement in political issues, gender equality). However, to keep to the required number of pages, we limit ourselves to the essentials.

this impact using a model that values the role of income distribution in capital formation in the credit market. Results of his study shows that inheritance and transfer operations by capitalist agents could reduce credit market frictions while generating more inequality. As such, by promoting capital accumulation, the increase in inequality is certain to occur when the efficiency of the financial market is targeted. With regard to the modelling of Saint-Paul and Verdier (1993), the results show that economic growth benefits from inequality. It allows those who belong to the higher ranks within the social hierarchy to use their influence against the implementation of abusive redistribution policies. Similarly, Li and Zou (1998) predict a positive relationship between inequality and growth. For Edin and Topel (1997) and Partridge (2006), rising inequality does not have a systematic effect but rather acts as a signal for skilled capitalists and workers to leave for the most unequal economies. Siebert (1998) and Bell and Freeman (2001) argue that inequality induces individuals to work harder and engage in innovation and risk-taking, which leads to higher economic growth. Forbes (2000) contests the existing belief that income inequality has a negative relationship with economic growth. He uses an improved data set on income inequality that not only reduces measurement error, but also allows estimation by a panel technique (panel of 45 countries over the period 1966-1995).

■ **Negative impact of inequality on economic development :**

Galor and Zeira (1993) and Piketty (1997) present cases where credit market imperfections affect the ability of poor households to invest in human and physical capital. Alesina and Rodrik (1994), Persson and Tabellini (1994) and Benabou (1996) raise the idea that disparities generate political pressure. This pressure leads to inefficient and forced redistribution processes of resources from the rich to the poor, which discourages investment and work effort. The impact on growth may have societal origins. According to Alesina and Perotti (1996), inequality encourages the poor to engage in illicit and anti-social activities such as crime and corruption. In turn, it makes them divert their resources from productive activities. Under unequal conditions, the individual may well consider holding back the economy as a whole when his or her share of production is relatively small, even though this may be detrimental to growth (Persson and Tabellini, 1991). According to Benhabib and Rustichini (1998) and much later Stiglitz (2015), the worst-off prefer a distributive system to efficient growth. Furthermore, studying the relationship between income growth and social mobility, Gottschalk (1997) argues that rising income inequality basically reflects a decline in the income of less skilled workers with an increase in the earnings of the more skilled. This generates a form of discrimination in the labour market that reduces the purchasing power of workers and domestic demand (Acemoglu, 1999).

Research has already attempted to precisely measure the impact of rising inequality on economic growth. Thorbeck & Charumilind's (2002) assessment of the impact of inequality in the long run shows a negative correlation of about 0.5 to 0.8 between inequality and growth. This relationship has been affirmed by the OECD report (2014) which shows that an increase in inequality of 3 Gini points implies a loss of 0.35 points of growth per year. Over a quarter of a century this cumulative loss amounts to 8.5% of GDP. These results confirm the idea that an unequal society grows at minimal speed (Bourguignon, 2012).

■ **Nonlinear effect of inequality on economic development :**

These studies show that the effect of inequality affects growth at different stages of economic development. Barro (2000) finds that inequality and growth have a non-linear relationship that remains unstable over time. In industrialized countries, the emergence of inequality means that the system has allowed a number of individuals to increase their income by starting a business or getting a better education. For poor countries, however, this relationship is rather negative. Benhabib (2003) argues that increases in inequality from low levels provide incentives to stimulate growth, while increases

beyond a certain point encourage rent-seeking (non-inclusive growth development). This idea has been reinforced by Chen (2003) and Banerjee and Duflo (2003), where the evolution of the inequality-growth relationship over the long term forms an inverted U-shaped curve. Using a general equilibrium growth model, Bandyopadhyay and Basu (2005) reveal that disparities and growth are positively correlated in economies with low barriers to knowledge diffusion, high technological skill intensity and high redistribution. On the contrary, they are negatively correlated in economies with different characteristics. Lin et al (2014) provide new findings on this relationship based on a study of panel data for 48 US states over the period 1945-2004: At lower levels of development, the effect of inequality on growth is significantly negative. However, it decreases along the growth process and then becomes significantly positive at higher levels of development.

■ **No relationship between inequality and economic development :**

Only a few studies have pointed to the complete absence of a relationship between inequality and economic performance. Assessing the impact of Economic Recovery Policies on poverty and inequality reduction via a CGE microsimulation model calibrated to Moroccan SAM of 1998, Touhami, Doccanfuso and Savard (2009) argue that achieving growth through sectoral increases (notably agriculture by 20% and tourism by 10%) leads to improved social mobility and increased global investment. But without having a direct impact on inequality.

3- Impact of income inequality on the general equilibrium structure

Social and economic inequality is a global, complex, and highly varied phenomenon. Given its significance and complexity, we restrict our attention to dealing with income inequality. This refers to the flow of resources available to feed one's consumption and savings (Hicks, 1948). The growth of income inequality generates a form of division that reinforces the gap between certain social classes, some refer to it as the great divide (Deaton, 2015). This social structure puts low-income individuals or young people who are unable to access the labour market far behind the highest social classes (Serfati, 2015; Alvaredo, 2018). Some epidemiologists consider that the less equal a society is, the better it has the capacity to produce in terms of citizenship and strengthening social factors (Wilkinson & Pickett, 2009).

The socioeconomic impact of income inequality is supported by many theoretical studies (Mdingi & Ho, 2021; Hombres & al., 2012). Therefore, to enhance the relevance of our approach, we will limit it to the inputs related to the modelling approach. Thus, this theoretical review discusses two components: (i) Conceptualization of the impact channels of income inequality on the macroeconomic equilibrium with reference to Walras' general equilibrium theory. (ii) Presentation of the key variables of the model that illustrate the extent of this socioeconomic impact.

3.1. Inclusion of income inequality concept into general equilibrium analysis

Economy in its global perception is represented by a circulation of monetary flows that results from the interactions of the market between at least three actors : Household, firm, and government². Under this illustration, the supply of factors of production (mainly labour and capital) by households generates a regular flow of income to finance their consumption expenditures. At the same time, the final consumption of households translates into sales, which in turn generate income for the general

² According to Walras' general equilibrium theory (1874) of the late 19th century, on one side, households, which are supposed to own the production factors. Second, firms, which rent factors from households for use in the production of goods subsequently purchased by households and other firms (intermediate consumption). The third actor is the government, which provides public goods that are consumed by households and firms

economic structure (sales for firms). In a system that is as intertwined as it is interactive, we imagine that an increase in household income inequalities could affect final consumption demand and thus threaten the maintenance of the fluidity of this monetary circulation. As a result, our approach to analyzing the impact of income inequality consists of following the propagation of the impact of an additional income gap between households on its economic environment as shown in Figure 1. We distinguish three types of externalities that affects this equilibrium:

Figure 1 : Household income inequality in the circulatory flow of the economy

Source: author (adapted from Mankiw, 2014)

- **Externalities (A):** These refer to the mutuality of effects between of income inequalities, labour markets, and capital market. The first connection to be highlighted concerns the returns to factors of production in proportion to households. On that note, Piketty (2013) confirms through his thesis on the forces of income divergence that capital incomes rise much more than labour incomes. This is reminiscent of Kalecki's (1954) thinking on the inevitable gap between workers and capitalists. The second connection relates to the impact of inequality on employment and capital. It is often discussed in studies that address the impact of inequality on growth. Some argue that unequal income growth can lead to an increase in national savings, as theorized by Kaldor (1957) in his thesis on the virtuous cycle. Others draw on Kuznets' work to confirm the positive impact that inequality can have on long-term growth (Forbes, 2000; Barro, 2000). On the contrary, several other studies reject this optimistic view (Banerjee & Duflo, 2003; Benhabib, 2003; Alesina & Rodrik, 1994; Persson and Tabellini, 1991; Bourguignon, 2015). Also, other studies testify to a qualitative impact of inequalities on the factors of

production: deterioration in the market supply of jobs, instability of financial markets, a trap in access to the financial market for the poor and intermediate classes, etc.

- **Externalities (B):** This concerns the impact of inequalities on the economic, social, and societal environment. Many different studies aim to establish a link between inequalities and the determinants of their socioeconomic impact (Ostry and al., 2014; Alesina and Rodrik, 1994; Galor and Zeira, 1993). The major finding of this review is that there is a negative causal relationship in both directions. Thus, an unequal environment is unfavorable to economic development in the long term for multiple reasons, mainly: recession of social cohesion, political instability (risk of riots), emergence of a sense of injustice (leading to increased crime, breakdown of the political system, lack of general confidence and others). This reinforces the idea that inequalities are evolutionary, multiform and above all cumulative (Piketty, 2013).

- **Externalities (C):** It relates to the impact of inequalities on public policies. We support the principle that the social impact of income inequality - relating to education and mental and physical health - exerts a heavy burden on public funds by increasing the need for investment and current expenditure on social policies. As for the societal impact, although difficult to measure, we believe that its factors have effects that are undeniable: Between the decline in trust, popular disengagement in political process, the rise of corruption and crime and the societal consequences of gender inequality.

3.2. Inequality impact assessment variables in the CGE model

We believe that impact of inequalities shall be occurred either directly through an economic channel or indirectly through a social channel according to the scientific community. Thus, as shown in Figure 2, our impact study focus on two group of variables : (i) Economic impact, which concerns economic growth (Kuznets, 1955), employment (Card & DiNardo, 2002; Acemoglu, 1999), financial stability (Brei & al., 2018; Beck & al., 2007), and trade openness (Daumal, 2013); (ii) Social impact, which includes wellbeing (Berg & Veenhoven, 2010 ; Alessina & al., 2004), education (Acemoglu & Pischke, 2001), and health (Leigh & al., 2009). Therefore, our modelling approach will focus on studying the variation in these variables to illustrate how inequality impacts the whole system.

Figure 2 : Description of the impact variables of income inequality whiting our CGE model

Source: Author

EMPIRICAL CONTEXT

Dynamics of income inequality in Morocco

Moroccan economy is running at "two speeds" in the fight against social imperfections. Although it is well ahead in its fight against absolute poverty, no one can say the same for its fight against relative poverty (Touhami et al., 2009). On the issue of inequality, the Oxfam report (2019) describes Morocco as the most unequal country in North Africa and in the most unequal half of countries in the world. Yet the level of inequality in Morocco is far from the average recorded in sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America or even some Middle Eastern countries, as shown in the following graph. but it remains unequal to its European trading partners, where the middle class in Morocco holds 37% of the share of national income compared to 45% on average in Europe.

Figure 3 : Income inequality in world region in comparison with Morocco, 2021

Source : WID, 2022

In this section we will first establish an overview of evidence on income inequality within Morocco collected from institutional reports. Then, we highlight the key factors that act as either sources or results of the expansion of inequality in Morocco.

I- Dynamics of income distribution in Morocco

In 2014, the top 10% of Moroccans received almost half of the national income. Although inequality in Morocco is not at the level of the most unequal countries in the world (where the share of national income held by the top decile is rather in the range of 50-55%), the share of the top decile in Moroccan national income has never gone below 47% since 1984 (WID, 2020). According to statistics from the World Inequality Database (2018), the average annual pre-tax income for an adult Moroccan is 276,886 Dh, equivalent to US\$28,962 and €25,279. This figure hides large disparities within income groups in that while the bottom half earns about 13,321 Dh on average (about \$1,400), the top decile earns 222,011 Dh (about \$23,300) which is more than 16 times the value of the poorest. Although lower than in the United States (i.e., 1/19), the ratio of 1/16 is double the gaps in China, where the income value of the top decile is about eight times that of the bottom half (Piketty, Saez & Zucman, 2016).

Figure 4 : Distribution of pre-tax national income in Morocco, 1984 - 2016

Source: WID, 2018

In Morocco, the income share of the elite represents 48.8% of the national income in 2018, against 14.64% for the poor half. As for the

middle class, the middle 40% of the social hierarchy, the average income per adult is 41,554 Dh (about 4346 dollars) of which their residual share in the national income is 36.54%.

Table 1 : Distribution of national income before tax in Morocco, 2018

Income group	Number of adults	Income limit (in Dh)	average income (in Dh)	Share in national income
Total	23 546 854	-	276 886	100%
50% lower	11 773 427	-	13 321	14,64%
40% middle	9 418 742	23 638	41 554	36,54%
10% upper	2 354 685	84 823	222 011	48,81%
1% upper	235 469	405 714	679 938	14,95%
0,1% upper	23 547	1 026 898	1 720 985	0,038%
0,01% upper	2 355	2 599 173	4 355 969	0,010%
0,001% upper	235	6 578 744	11 025 356	0,002%

Source: Author (Calculated from WID database)

In the long term, we can see that the structure of pre-tax income has generally not changed over the past four decades, especially for the lower half of the population. The distribution of national income is marked by extreme inequality throughout the redistribution, even in the richest 10% of the population. The 236,000 wealthiest Moroccan adults, or about 1% of the population, receive 14.95% of the national income, giving them an average annual income of 679,938 Dh (or \$71,123). Like this top decile, the pre-tax incomes per year of the 0.1%, 0.01% and 0.001% of the richest are estimated on average at 1.7 Million Dh (equivalent to \$180,019), 4.3 Million Dh (equivalent to \$455,645) and 11 Million Dh (equivalent to \$1.153 million).

For the top of the social hierarchy in Morocco, pre-tax income growth has not been subject to a continuous increase over time. Since the early 1980s, income growth has been divided into four distinct phases. The first phase began in 1984, coinciding with the adoption of SAP, when Morocco was officially under the tutelage of the

IMF and IBRD (Akesbi, 1985). Until the early 1990s, this period was marked by continuous growth of the top ten thousandth. In 1990, the richest 0.01% of the Moroccan adult population received an average income of 18 million dirhams. This is twice as much as at the beginning of this phase, namely 7.5 million in 1984. According to these statistics, the top 1% and 0.001% of the population experienced a quasi-stagnation during this period. The top thousandth (top 0.1%) increased but not as much as the top 0.01%. We can see that the economic regulation brought about by the Structural Adjustment Program (PAS) served more a minority, 0.09% of the Moroccan population at the time. This category includes all but the top 0.001%, the equivalent of 918 to 1136 people from 1984 to 1991.

Figure 5 : Evolution of top 1% of the average income in Morocco, 1984 – 2017 (million MAD)

Source: Author (Calculated from WID database)

The second phase covers almost the entire 1990s, from 1991 to 1998. During this period, the proportion that experienced an increase in their share, namely the top 0.1% and 0.01%, largely declined. The 0.01% share saw its income fall by an average of 8 million, to an average income of 10.2 million in 1998. During this period, the upper decile as a whole experienced the lowest growth of the entire period studied, compared to a relatively upward evolution of the Moroccan middle class (the middle 40%).

Although this phase coincides with an observed irregularity in the decline of poverty, we note that the second phase is the time when inequalities in Morocco were relatively attenuated, and the middle class was reinforced.

Figure 6 : Evolution of top 10% gross income in Morocco, 1984-2017

Source: Author (Calculated from WID database)

The third phase is the period before the economic crash of 2007 following the subprime crisis. During this third phase (1998-2007), the Moroccan economy grew fairly consistently on average 4% per year, with rates that can exceed 7.5% (HCP, 2013 and Eurostat, 2013). Despite still being tied to its agricultural aspect, in 1999, the Moroccan economy took its first steps towards becoming one of the most diversified economies in Francophone Africa. At its peak, economic growth was both supported by agricultural revenues, due to the always favorable climatic conditions at the time, and the promotion of certain tertiary sectors (tourism, offshore, finance and others) as well as the development of the land sector supported by the promotion of bank credit financing.

Withing this prosperous environment, the incomes of the wealthy Moroccans, particularly those of the 0.1%, grew progressively until 2006, when these incomes recorded a dominant value. In just one year, the average pre-tax income of the top 0.01% rose from MAD 13.5 million in

2006 to MAD 29.9 million in 2007. Similarly, the top decile as a whole is experiencing growth similar to the growth it experienced during the first phase from 1984 to 1991.

Figure 7 : Evolution of economic growth and value added by sector in morocco, 1984-2017

Source: Author (Calculated from WID database)

The fourth phase (2008-2017) is marked by a downward trend for upper incomes, especially for the shares relating to the richest percentile. On the other hand, the 9% who reside just below this percentile experienced a higher growth than in the other phases studied, which claims a reinforcement of this share of the population to the detriment of the richest 1%, allowing for a kind of income redistribution in Morocco. This income distribution is also expressed by the reduction of inequality in the Gini sense over this period, where Morocco has gone below the critical 40% mark, from 40.6% in 2007 to 39.5% in 2014 (HCP, 2016; DEPF, 2018).

Over the period of the 1990s, we argue that a relative reduction in inequality is accompanied by a succession of significant rates of agricultural value added with greater volatility. Does the reduction in inequality have an impact on this agricultural production? Using the simulations provided in our Ex-ante approach, we will study

the variation in the value added of this sector as a result of the variation in income disparities between representative households.

II- Expanding Inequality Factors in Morocco

1. Failure of education and health to ensure income convergence and social mobility

Education and health are the two key determinants that fuel the widening gap between different social groups in Morocco. The various institutional reports reveal that any underperformance in these factors will inevitably be reflected in social gaps (ONDH, 2017; DEPF, 2019; CESE, 2019), as will a social performance indicator. In this case, irrelevance in the field of education and health has the effect of reducing the equality of an individual's chances with regard to their ability to achieve social mobility (Sen, 2012).

1.1. Education

Although education is perceived as the equalizer par excellence (El Aoufi and Hanchane, 2016), the inefficiency of this sector is fatal in amplifying inequalities in Morocco (DEPF, 2019). Through benchmarking that compares Morocco's indicators to similar countries established by the DEPF (2019), Morocco is ranked last in terms of educational inequality with a record rate of 55.5% in the Gini sense. According to the Human Development Report, education accounts for 27.5% of the sources of economic inequality in the kingdom (ONDH, 2017). Morocco suffers from strong inequalities in education, which has an amplifying effect on social inequalities. Notwithstanding the public programs undertaken as part of the overhaul of the education system (ONDH, 2017), the average length of schooling remains low by international standards. However, this indicator has evolved since the 1980s.

In addition, disparities are manifested by public expenditure on education according to the different social groups, particularly for secondary and higher education. Indeed, 29% of Moroccans enrolled in secondary and higher

education belong to the two upper deciles D9 and D10. On the other hand, only 10% of Moroccans belonging to the two poorest deciles D1 and D2 are enrolled in this education cycle. Thus, the 2016 NAEP study reveals that the impact of social inheritance (social capital, prerequisites, parents' situation and others) on student performance amounts to almost 80%, compared to 20% of the academic inputs they receive at school or educational institution (CSEFRS, 2017).

Figure 8 : Comparing educational inequalities in Morocco to similar countries, Gini 2015

Source: DEPF, 2019

This has a greater impact on learning in a public-school institution due to its inability to mitigate the effects of social inequalities due to the lack of appropriate pedagogical strategies and methods for struggling students (TIMSS, 2015). As a result, the gaps in academic performance between students with parents who have at least a university degree and those who do not, are reflected in a difference in the report card that amounts to 64 points in mathematics and 62 points in science (CSEFRS, 2017).

In Morocco, the average score of students in mathematics in the fourth year of primary school is estimated at 377. This score is largely low given that the international average is 500 points (TIMSS, 2015). Furthermore, educational inequalities place a heavy burden on Morocco's development. First, the cost of non-emancipation and the burden of individual underperformance: These inequalities stimulate school failure, repetition and dropout. Similarly, they fuel the exclusion of those who do not

manage to join the school system because of their social vulnerability. Due to the frustration caused by this rejection, non-adherents to the school systems find themselves exposed to delinquency and violence. As mentioned in the theoretical chapter on the impact of inequalities, this has not only a social but also a societal impact.

Figure 9 : Evolution of education inequality indicators in Morocco, 1982-2014

Source: DEPF, 2019

1.2. Health

If education guarantees equal opportunities, health is no less important. In Morocco, various institutional indicators show that social inequalities largely affect inequalities in access to health care and life expectancy (ENSPF, 2011; DEPF, 2019). For every thousand children born alive to poor Moroccan households, 33.9 of them suffer infant mortality. In contrast, for children from better-off households, this rate drops to 18.7 per thousand (ENSPF, 2011). As we saw earlier in the US system, medical costs weigh heavily on household expenses, especially in the absence of adequate medical coverage. Indeed, in Morocco, the financing of these costs is mainly ensured by the head of the household and via direct payments which amount to more than half of total health expenditure. On average, this share is 50.7%, while for the bottom 20% of the scale, it can be as high as 89.7%, compared to 56.2% for those at the top (ENCDM, 2014).

Given that until the end of 2020, the Moroccan health care was described as a system "under construction" by the National Health Insurance Agency (ANAM). Thus, the privileged, because of their socio-professional situation, can benefit from more medical coverage than others. Only those who have a suitable job (mainly state civil servants or holders of a post declared to the CNSS) can benefit from medical coverage, while all informally employed people do not have access to it. This unequal distribution also has a special dimension. In 2007, the average rate of medical coverage was 15.8%. In urban areas, almost a quarter of households are covered, while in rural areas only 3.9% of households have medical coverage (DEPF, 2019). 76.3% of households nationwide had no medical coverage in 2007, and this rate was much higher in rural areas, at 93.3%. In that same year, 23.7% of households had at least one member covered by a health insurance scheme, of which 12.4% were fully covered and 11.3% were only partially covered (DEPF, 2019).

Figure 10 : Health indicators by social class in Morocco, 2019

Source: DEPF, 2019

In 2019, as a result of public investment, the coverage rate for all schemes combined reached 70%, the equivalent of an increase of 54 points in just 12 years, the equivalent of 25.2 million beneficiaries. In terms of cost, this represents a value of 9.4 billion dirhams for the basic compulsory health insurance scheme (AMO) for employees, civil servants and all public or private pensioners, which includes 32.1% of drug costs

and 51% of expenditure provided to people with long-term illnesses (ANAM, 2020).

Figure 11 : Distribution of health facilities by Moroccan region and population, 2018

Source: HCP, 2019

Despite the introduction of the RAMED scheme, the DEPF reports (2019) that only 5% of the lowest quintile have medical coverage. On this basis, we assume that inequalities in access to health care persist, given that this scheme is hampered by a weak health supply at both national and regional level: the medical density index states the availability of only one doctor per 1000 inhabitants. Although this value is identical to the average for the region, it is the lowest in the North African region (World Factbook, 2020).

Moreover, this offer is also constrained by the reduced number of medical staff and the inadequacy of the infrastructure dedicated to health, particularly in the public sector. Also, the number of medical staff is very poorly distributed between the different regions of the kingdom (the southern region is totally disadvantaged in terms of health), even to the

point of inconsistency (the region of Fez has almost 15% of public health establishments while it only hires 10% of the doctors). As for the medical density by region, we can see that in 2019, for every 10,000 Moroccans, there are at least 12 doctors in the region of Rabat - Salé - Kenitra, while there will be only 3 for the region of Draa Tafilalet.

2. Impact of budgetary and fiscal policies on income redistribution

Social inclusion is of great concern to the Moroccan public authorities. Referring to the reports of the Ministry of Finance (2018), we will deduce that the reinforcement of social factors is placed at the heart of the action of public policy budgeting. To this end, we will try to present the extent of the role of these budgetary policies in the fight against income inequalities in Morocco.

2.1. Impact of fiscal policies

The regressive effect of tax policies can be seen as a source of increasing inequality in some countries, such as the United States (Osberg et al., 2004). Since independence, the evolution of the tax system in Morocco has been characterized by the multiplicity of direct and indirect taxes until the mid-1980s. Currently, the tax system is structured around four main pillars, namely direct taxes (IR, IS and other similar taxes), indirect taxes (VAT and TIC), customs duties and registration and stamp duties and TSAVA (DEPF, 2019). During the last two decades, tax revenues have increased sufficiently. Despite the counter-effective effects of the 2008 crisis, the average annual increase in tax revenues in Morocco is 6.3% (Hrach, 2020). In 2017, tax revenues were estimated at 225.5 billion dirhams, which represents about 26.5% of GDP (MEF, 2018). The structure of tax revenues in Morocco is marked by a clear rebound in direct taxes due to the efficiency of IS revenues, which increased by more than 5 percentage points during the period under review, while IR tax revenues declined relatively. Indirect taxes, on the other hand, increased significantly in 2011, especially VAT, whose share has exceeded the 30% threshold since 2011.

Figure 12 : Tax revenue in Morocco, 2004-2018

Source: MEF, 2019

2.1.1 Impact of value added tax (TVA)

Because of the structure of tax revenues supported by indirect taxes, Oxfam (2019) considers that the Moroccan system is far from fair. Indeed, TVA, by its nature as an indirect tax, is highly regressive as its burden on the budget of the poorest is relatively greater (Lustiger and Higgins, 2017; Oxfam, 2019; Ehrhart et al., 2020). This regressivity is also reinforced by the wide application of the single 'flat tax' rate, which even concerns certain basic foodstuffs, and the absence of derogatory rates that are more taxable for the richest (e.g. the 30% rate applied to luxury goods provided for in the jurisdiction, which dates from before 1993). According to the CESE (2012), the inequalities caused by the inefficiency of TVA are due to the fact that it does not apply to many sectors of economic activity, either because of exemptions or because they are part of the informal sector. This creates a counter-efficiency that weighs on the competitiveness of the non-exempt formal sector (EESC, 2012). Although the AFD study (2020) shows that TVA only has an impact on poverty. The fact remains that indirect taxes are not equipped to reduce inequality, even apart from TVA. The example of the domestic consumption tax (TIC) on tobacco is rather regressive (Ehrhart et al., 2020).

2.1.2 Impact of income tax (IR)

As for the income tax, despite its more pro-poor nature, it is no less unequal. Because it has a less

progressive scale, it falls more heavily on the average taxpayer working in the formal sector, such as civil servants. On the other hand, many potential taxpayers, mainly in the informal sector, escape it, namely traders, entrepreneurs, farmers and professionals who operate informally or opaquely due to a lack of control, leaving three quarters of the revenue to be paid by employees. As a result, income tax is a tax on a small minority of wage earners (Akesbi, 2013).

Figure 13 : Illustration of progressive structuring of income tax in Morocco

Source: Autor

2.2 Impact of public transfers on income inequalities

In Morocco, public spending on education and health has contributed to the reduction of inequalities by -7.5% (Ehrhart et al., 2020). In addition to transfers for operating and investing in these sectors, others are paid directly to incomes in the form of cash or quasi-cash transfers. These transfers contribute to reducing vulnerability and inequality, but to a limited extent. The limited effect of these transfers is explained in particular by the low budgets allocated to appropriate social programs. This overall assessment, however, conceals differentiated results according to the type of transfer. On the one hand, family allowances, whose contribution to the formation of market income remains sufficiently visible, present a positive concentration coefficient of 0.232 (Ehrhart et al., 2020).

Figure 13: Shares of transfers in market income by decile in Morocco

Source: Ehrhart et al., 2020

The progressive nature of these allocations is reflected in their contribution to the reduction of inequality and vulnerability. For conditional cash transfer programs, such as the Tayssir program, these are rightly seen as an appropriate targeting instrument for the poorest. However, the results of the AFD study (2020) show that their impact on vulnerability and inequality reduction is low. As regards programs to support schooling and training (school housing, school canteens, school transport, 1 million school bags, university scholarships), although their progressive nature is confirmed, their impact in terms of reducing inequalities and vulnerability is limited, due to the weakness of their budget allocations (Ehrhart et al., 2002).

3. Unequal and inefficient labour market

A review of the various national institutional reports dealing with this issue (DEPF, 2018; DEPF, 2019; CESE, 2019; ONDH, 2017) confirms that structural failures in the labour market have an impact on income, particularly wage income. Inequality in access to employment opportunities is often associated with discriminatory factors, such as gender, age or place of residence (between rural and urban). Indeed, strong disparities persist in women's access to employment. Their activity rate is

significantly lower than that of men and this situation has hardly changed in more than a decade: from 2005 to 2016, the gap between male and female employment has remained stable throughout the period (from 27.9% to 23.6% for women and from 76.2% to 70.8% for men). On the other hand, working women are more vulnerable to unemployment, with a rate of 10.9% in 2015, compared to 8.9% for men (DEPF, 2019).

Figure 14 : Gender parity in the Moroccan labour market, 2010-2016

Source: HCP, 2017

Apart from the female gender, the inability of young people to find a job weighs not only on their capacities, but also on the capacity of the households to which they belong. Indeed, Moroccan growth is failing to create enough jobs to insert young people into the labour market (DEPF, 2018). At the beginning of 2018, the overall unemployment rate was 10.5% and that of young people reached 25%. However, these figures do not reflect the high proportion of underemployment and informal work in the rural population.

The low integration of women into the labour market, in particular, is alarming: currently, only 31.9% of women in the rural world are employed (Harbouze et al., 2019). Among other causes, this gender discrimination is due to the great regional disparities in the labour market. In rural areas, the supply of jobs is much smaller than in urban areas. Social aspects such as gender, education and age also play an important role, which further complicates the job search.

4. Middle class in difficulty

According to the work of El Aoufi and Hanchane (2016), Morocco is undergoing a process of "*Demoyennisation*" of its population. This term defines a weakening or disappearance of its middle classes, thus generating a deepening in the social hierarchy. In this case, any distributive approach would not be able to strengthen social cohesion (El Aoufi, 2009). In fact, any economy where the share of the middle class is low does not allow social cohesion to be measured in terms of redistributive justice (Putnam, 2008; Ferroni, 2008).

In Morocco, the trajectory of the middle classes has undergone three inflection points (El Aoufi and Hanchane, 2016). The first dates from the 1973 Moroccanisation law, which aimed to promote a middle class of national capital owners. However, this vision was not realized for two main reasons: (i) the presence of rent mechanisms that favor the exploitation of this capital only by the wealthiest; (ii) structural deficiencies in the purchasing power of the middle class limit their enjoyment of the credits granted under the Moroccanisation Fund.

The application of the Structural Adjustment Program (PAS) is considered a second source of middle-class failure. Considering the budgetary constraint as well as the achievement of the objectives of reinforcing the sustainability of external debt, PAS affected the purchasing power of the middle classes and reduce their standard of consumption, particularly in the mid-1980s. Ten years later, the social orientation of macro-economic policies and its affirmation in the framework of the INDH reinforced this process of downgrading (Maurin, 2009).

According to the HCP survey (2009), the middle class is bypassed between those with a monthly income equal to or greater than 2,800 DH and those with an income of less than 6,736 DH. This category represents 55.8% of the total population against 39.4% for the poor categories and 3.2% for the rich class. In 2007, this class had 66% of income, 65.5% of consumption expenditure and 72% of savings (HCP, 2009).

In terms of income, this class is highly heterogeneous. As a result, the configuration of the 53% belonging to the middle class is structured as follows: 28% belong to the upper fraction of the middle class (monthly income between 5308 Dh and 6736 Dh), 42% form the intermediate layer (monthly income between 3500 Dh and 5308 Dh), and 30% constitute the lower category (monthly income below 3500 Dh). In terms of socio-professional status, the middle class is composed mainly, up to 80% of lower and intermediate level profiles (civil servants, employees, craftsmen and skilled workers). As a result, salaried workers account for the largest share of the sources of income of this class, estimated at 44,5% overall, compared with 30,3% for individual businesses and 13,3% for transfers.

The expenditure structure shows that the decline of the middle class affects more the lower strata, those who are close to the vulnerable and poor (El Aoufi and Hanchane, 2016). Spending 12% more than their income, the lower strata of the middle-class resort to debt to cover current consumption needs, which amounts to 71.2% compared to 55.8% for the intermediate category and 54.6% for the upper fraction of this same class. At the same time, access to property credit and credit for household equipment and the acquisition of means of transport remains too limited for the middle classes as a whole (25.1% and 15.9%, respectively), reflecting an objective situation of insecurity in the face of the vagaries of the cost of living for 58% of the middle classes. This explains the bias in the perception of inequalities suffered by this section of the Moroccan population and their impact on the conduct of their citizens. However, it would be prejudicial not to mention the majority share of subsidized products that the middle-class benefits from.

5. Uncontrolled wealth accumulation

The uncontrolled growth of wealth has a consequent impact on the failure of income distribution (Piketty, 2013). Moroccan taxation is described as partially unfair because of its

failure to regulate capital accumulation due to the near non-existence of wealth taxes (Oxfam, 2019). These limitations are also reinforced by loopholes, exemptions or circumventions causing huge wealth gaps.

Since statistics on the issue are not available, trying to assess the loss of state revenue related to the absence of such a tax, especially as regards both the threshold and the tax rate, is far from being suitable for our empirical approach. However, a comparative study of the experiences of some OECD countries states that: In France, for example, total wealth taxation, in the broad sense, represented 4.4% of GDP in 2017, or €100.8 billion, of which €64 billion (2.8% of GDP) was from taxation of real estate capital and €5 billion (0.2% of GDP) from wealth tax. In the United States and the United Kingdom, revenues from wealth tax amounted to 4.2% of GDP in 2017, or USD 810 billion and GBP 85 billion respectively.

In comparison, Morocco has only a tax on the ownership of real estate, with revenues of 0.7% of GDP, or about 7.4 billion dirhams, a paltry figure. There is no wealth tax, nor inheritance or gift tax, and the rest of the wealth tax is based on financial and capital transactions (1.3% of GDP, or 1.3 billion dollars). It should be noted that the taxation of inheritance and transmission has been modified in the 2019 Finance Act. From now on, the taxable base will be the market value of the property at the time of the transmission of wealth. However, the rate retained, 1% of the value, is negligible and has no impact on the intergenerational reproduction of wealth gaps.

6. Access to affordable housing issues

In Morocco, the structure of household expenditure is largely dominated by food and energy expenditure, but even more so by housing (HCP, 2014). The category of housing is correlated with the standard of living of households. Only 12% of modern dwellings belong to the lowest quintile, compared to 61% occupied by the highest quintile. For precarious or unhealthy housing, about 71% of rural

households reside in adobe houses and 17% in solid houses (El Aoufi and Hanchane, 2016).

Despite a supply that is strongly supported by the sector's professional actors (state, developer and bank), the mismatch between this supply and market demand, particularly for the modest buyer, causes some sort of inequality in access to housing due to insufficient resources, structural shortages and the anarchic and informal development of precarious and unhealthy housing patterns (El Aoufi and Hanchane, 2016). Despite the support of public initiatives, such as 'Cities without Slums' or 'FOGARIM', many constraints persist with regard to the development of accessibility to housing for the poorest. On the other side of the hierarchy, the lack of control over access to land for the privileged, leading to the expansion of land disparities in Morocco (Labari, 2019). Among these constraints, we mainly mention

■ Inefficiency into reducing housing insecurity:

The inability to cover all defaulting households that are the primary target of their implementation. Due to the incompleteness of construction operations and the insufficiency or absence of socio-collective facilities (schools, health centers, ovens, hammams, etc.), urban integration remains problematic.

■ Inadequate financing for poor households:

In addition to these shortcomings associated with the supply of social housing, financing difficulties are added due to the lack of solvency or the low income of these households. This is partly due to the financial cost of housing credit for social housing, which remains high. Similarly, the mobilization of small and micro-savings is rather limited by the absence of a regulatory framework adapted to the specific characteristics of microfinance institutions and a diversified offer of savings products that takes into account the needs of low-income or irregular households (Ragbi and Bijou, 2017).

■ Uncontrolled price increases:

In theory, families with higher socio-economic status are willing to pay higher housing prices to live in more homogeneous neighborhoods (Bayer et al. 2005). This need for prestige has characterized the market for land goods and services, ranging from the

price of land or premises to the cost of construction and capital goods. On average, the price index for building materials increased by 1.42 points from 2017 to 2018. This increase in prices affects the cost of property development, which puts pressure on the capacities of the poorest.

7. Vulnerability to international shocks

As in most developing countries, the Covid-19 health crisis has driven home the point about inequality in Morocco (Bowled, 2020). In addition to the fact that inequality may act as a transmitter of infection (Faheem et al., 2020), other studies have focused on the impact that this health crisis may have on social disparities (Furceri et al., 2020; Davillas and Jones, 2021; Wiwad et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2021). As the pandemic has perpetuated an economic crisis, unemployment rates will rise dramatically, and the weakening of social safety nets further threatens health and social insecurity. Faced with the risk of the virus spreading, the preventive strategy of containment is one of the most widely adopted responses in the world. However, this is not without risk, particularly in terms of its impact on socio-economic fundamentals (Lopez and Rodo, 2020).

In Morocco, recourse to the choice of confinement is capable of causing a deterioration in all the indices of the standard of living. The collective study of the ERECA research team (2020) presents a simulation of this impact, showing that its magnitude differs according to residence. The results show that the rural world has been more affected by this. This has contributed to the aggravation of inequalities between the two environments of residence. However, the aid offered to households has allowed the partial mitigation of the shock caused by the health crisis on the one hand (Aazi, Audibert et al., 2020). Although the simulations consider two scenarios (optimistic and pessimistic), we have taken only the average to design these graphs in Figure 15.

Figure 15 : Simulation of the impact of Covid 19 crisis in Morocco

Source: Author (based on Aazi et al., 2020)

METHODOLOGY

Research approach & modelling strategy

1. Research approach : How did we design our research?

In the methodology section, we note that the present study is founded upon three main components: (i) Theoretical and conceptual component; (ii) the empirical dimension (data analysis on income inequality dynamics in Morocco); (iii) Modelling & simulations. Following a positioning that tends towards the positivist posture³, our research approach is guided by Livet's triangular model that links theory to empirics to modelling for validation and interpretation, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 16 : Methodological triangle connecting theory, empirics and modelling

Source: Author (based on Livet et al., 2010; 2014; Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

The literature review was designed with the ambition to achieve three research principles: Exhaustiveness, multi-disciplinarity and in-depth funnel analysis. While the extended version of the study contains more details, the short version focuses obtaining a relevant and concise review. The purpose is to provide a theoretical background to the simulation of the impact of inequalities. The analysis of the dynamics of income inequality is an essential component in our research. Although modelling remains a priority in addressing the central problem, it is limited by its static dimension. Moreover, CGE modelling does not consider non-market factors that may influence the development of inequality in Morocco. Therefore, studying data on income distribution patterns and the specific determinants of inequality in the Moroccan case is bound to enrich our understanding of the subject.

2. Modelling tool used : CGE model

Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) modelling is a simulation device perfect for impact studies and policy assessment. It is based on a consistent theoretical foundation and a closed accounting system, called the Social Accounting Matrix (SAM), where prices and quantities are endogenously determined. For this study, we used a national and static CGE Model adapted from the PEP1-1 model

³ Our positivist posture is in line with the principles of Auguste Comte's positivism (1858) because it is sustained by quantifiable observations that lead to the establishment of a theoretical and empirical analysis of the subject.

and calibrated on the Moroccan SAM (2016) distributed as follows : (i) 19 branches consolidated into three main sectors (Primary sector related to agriculture and fishing ; Secondary sector related to industries and manufacturing ; Tertiary sector for private and public services) (ii) 2 factors of production: labour and capital ; (iii) 7 economic agents: Government, firms, rest of the world (ROW) and 4 households, including 3 additional accounts represent taxes (indirect taxation "TI", direct taxation "TD" and import taxation "TM"). The elasticities (CET and CES) relating to agent behaviour, headcount and income of each household are taken from the database of the High Commission of Planning of Morocco (Ref: General Survey of Population and Housing of 2014).

3. Modelling strategy : How to integrate inequality assessment into CGEM?

The procedure for incorporating the study of income inequality between parameterized households into our modelling is based on two overarching approaches. First, we divide the representative households in such a way that their level of inequality is consistent with inequality in Morocco, namely 39.34% in the Gini sense. Secondly, we provide external shocks capable of generating either income convergence or divergence. Then we study the variations in the targeted variables.

3.1. Income inequality measuring approach

The measurement of income inequality on the CGEM is carried out via the Gini index (1921). In addition to the cumulative income share data (Y_k), we use the headcount data (X_k) that aggregates each of the representative households modelled.

$$I_{Gini} = \left| 1 - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (X_{k+1} - X_k)(Y_{k+1} - Y_k) \right|$$

3.2. CGEM Simulation strategy

To stimulate the income inequality in CGEM, we implement two types of public policies:

- ❖ **Tax policy :** This consists of establishing an overtaxation of household incomes via a direct tax (DT). As shown later in the simulation plan, this overtaxation targets a variation of 25% on urban household incomes and 15% on rural household incomes.
- ❖ **Mixed policy:** This policy is composed of a fiscal and tax policy. The fiscal component uses the same measures as the first policy, while the second consists of a 20% increase in public current expenditure. The interest is to reduce the effect of the increase in government revenue generated by the direct tax on household income.

Regarding the policies explained previously, the simulation strategy is formulated to set up different scenarios where changes in income inequality impact the macroeconomic aggregates of the model. Our simulation strategy is summarized in three parts:

- **Simulation of the increase in inequality:** The impact of overtaxing the non-poor against a reduction in the direct tax on the poor is simulated in **SIM1**, **SIM3** and **SIM5**. Although these policies aim at reducing the income gap between poor (UPH and RPH) and non-poor (UNPH and RNPH) households through taxation, the results show a relative increase in inequality in the sense of Gini, especially in **SIM1** (increase in inequality of +0.15%).
- **Simulation of the reduction of inequalities:** The impact of overtaxing the poor against a reduction of the direct tax on the non-poor is simulated in **SIM2**, **SIM4** and **SIM6**, which, in parallel with the other simulations, lead to a decrease in household income inequalities, especially in **SIM2** (variation of -0.15% in the Gini sense).

KEY MODELING RESULTS

Socioeconomic impact of income inequality in Morocco

I- Effects of implemented shocks on income redistribution in CGEM

To provide a better understanding on the extent of the impact of the simulated shocks on inequality, our approach distinguishes these simulations into two groups: the impact of fiscal policy and the impact of mixed policy. Thus, the first group includes only SIM1 and SIM2. According to the results, we specify that the impact of SIM1 leads to results that are perfectly inverse to those of SIM2. In fact, reducing income inequality through SIM2 leads to an increase in income, mainly in transfer income. This increase is more beneficial to non-poor households, hence the increase in their shares of YHTR of (+0.2%) for UPH and (+0.1%) for RPH.

Figure 17 : Impact of fiscal policy on household income and inequality

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

The second group includes SIM3, SIM4, SIM5, and SIM6. We also add SIM0 to establish a baseline value for their changes. In contrast to the first group, inequality results of this second group are more pronounced in terms of the reduction in inequality, with a reduction that varies between (-1.62%) and (-

1.30%). Assuming that the change in income inequality index for SIM0 is (-1.46%), we consider only those simulations that have decreased beyond this point, namely SIM4 and SIM6. Considering these assumptions, we note that fiscal restructuring in favor of poor households limits the positive effects generated by this expansionary fiscal policy, mostly in terms of limiting the equalizing effect of the increase in public spending.

Figure 18 : Impact of the mixed policy on household income and inequality

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

Other than household income, these inequalities have a negative impact on the economic structure. Indeed, SIM1 causes a decrease in business revenues of (-0.35%). Instead, SIM4 and SIM6 cause an increase in firms' income at a similar rate of (+2.27%). Meanwhile, inequality has a stimulating effect on the public and external revenues. For the public agent, we relate this effect to the increase in tax revenue generated by the overtaxation of households. For the external agent, we find that the reduction in domestic firm's revenue is beneficial for the rest of the world.

This is more strongly demonstrated by SIM4 and SIM6 results, where the decrease in the income of the "rest of the world" agent reflects a gain from the exchange, as it coincides with an increase in firm's revenue.

Figure 19 : Results of the simulations of the impact on the income of economic agents

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

Given all results on the impact on revenue, the most economically beneficial policies are SIM4 and SIM6. However, we strongly recommend the policy simulated by SIM6. Although both confirm a positive correlation between inequality reduction and household income enhancement, SIM6 is technically and socially more adequate. As a matter of fact, SIM6 policy raises the incomes of the poorest without applying any tax pressure on household incomes. We find that an income tax cut of 25% for urban poor households and 15% for rural poor households allows them to increase their UPH income by (+5.844%) and their RPH income by (+3.036%) respectively, with a Gini index that decreases from 39.4% to 38.7%.

II- Impact on the behaviour of different households

Our results demonstrate that inequality has an impact on the individual households' behaviour, which are illustrated in the following three main components: consumption, savings, and transfers between agents.

1. Impact on household consumption

Income inequality increases consumption inequality and reduces the overall level of household consumption. As the results of the simulations show, the level of consumption inequality increases in response to all shocks simulated, except for SIM0. In fact, any variation in income affects inequalities in

household consumption demand. However, according to SIM2, the reduction in inequality increases the level of final household consumption, in particular that of the UNPH agent by (+1.96%), which represents 15% of overall consumption. Conversely, the UPH household increases its consumption expenditure in SIM1.

Figure 20 : Results of simulations of the impact on household consumption

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

2. Impact on household savings

According to SIM1 results, income inequality increases savings' inequality and reduces national household savings. Noteworthy is that UPH increased both its savings and its consumption.

Figure 21 : Results of impact simulations on household savings

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

When a fiscal policy is added to SIM1's fiscal policy, in this case SIM3, UPH further increases its consumption and savings. We find that UPH's consumption and saving behaviour is particularly highly sensitive to increases in income. As for his rural counterpart, it is only savings that are sensitive to these shocks, in particular the mixed policy.

3. Impact on the mutuality of household transfers

The structure of income shows that transfers represent a total of 27% of household income. In fact, they are the least unequal, having a Gini index of 30.6%. The increase in inequality leads to a reduction in the mutuality of transfers between the different agents in the model, even reducing transfers from abroad, according to SIM1. In terms of household transactions, poor households' transfers to the government decreased by (-0.77%). This rate is near the decline in transfers issued by RNPH (-0.73%). In the case of the upper household UNPH, the issuance of transfers decreased only by (-0.33%). Similarly, UNPH is the only agent whose decrease in transfer receipt exceeds its issuance. However, its impact remains minor, given that UNPH's income represents only 17% of its total income.

The variation in the level of transfer inequalities per simulation is almost the same for all the shocks except for the fiscal policy simulated at SIM0 (inequalities increase by almost 8% compared to the baseline level). However, it is important to keep in mind that the redistribution hierarchy of transfer income is different from that of total income, where the higher income share is held mainly by rural households. To this end, the increase in inequality implies more transfers to RPH and RNPH. Therefore, the increase in income in SIM4 and SIM6 for urban income relatively reduces transfer inequalities. Our findings confirm that the redistribution of transfer income has a regulatory function on the level of inequality in

Morocco. Similarly, a fiscal stimulus policy will strengthen transfers to the rural environment, while favoring the RNPH agent. As for the non-household agents, the most significant decrease in emissions is linked to the external agent ROW. Technically, the increase in inequality reduces external transfers and, thus, increases income for this external agent.

Figure 22 : Impact of the simulations on transfers between agents (SIM1 & SIM2)

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

III- Impact on the components of market equilibrium

Once the impact of income inequality on household behaviour has been highlighted, this section focuses on the impact on the various components of market equilibrium by presenting the results of the impact on supply and demand aggregates.

1. Impact on aggregate demand

The presentation of the impact on aggregate demand concerns the exposition of impact results of the factors of production and commodities.

1.1. Impact on factors of production's demand

The structure of demand for factors of production by branch is calibrated so that most branches are capital-dependent, except for fishing (PAQ), public services

(ADM), social services (MNO), and other industries (AIND). By sector, we note that an increase in income inequality following SIM1 reduces the demand for factors of production in the primary sector of agriculture and the tertiary sector of services.

Figure 23 : Distribution of factors of production by branch

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

Figure 24 : Impact on the demand for factors of production by sector

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

In contrast, it has a stimulating effect on the secondary sector of industry and manufacturing. The most impactful effect is associated with agriculture with a decrease in labour demand of (-0.66%) and a decrease in capital demand of (-0.72%). This effect is reflected in a risk of increased unemployment and the weakening of return on capital. We also find that introducing a fiscal policy has a negative effect on the demand for capital in all private sectors. Regarding employability, the mixed policy shock has a mixed effect depending on the sector of activity: negative effect for the secondary industrial sector, positive for the service sector and mixed for the primary sector of agricultural and fishing.

1.2. Impact on commodities demand

Demand on goods and services market is negatively impacted by the growth of income inequality in SIM1. For the mixed policy simulations that result in a relative reduction in inequality (SIM3 and SIM5), the commodities where consumption has declined are those belonging to the primary sector of agriculture and fishing (AGRP and PAQP) as well as education, health, and other social services (MNOP).

Figure 25 : Impact of the simulations on consumption by branch in SIM1

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

Since these scenarios aim to simulate an eventual increase in income inequality during a period of sustained public policy stimulus, we consider that this increase in inequality has a reducing effect on the demand for these products that are fundamental to household social progress.

1.3. Impact on supply : Output and value added

To assess the impact on production, we study the variation in GDP. We distinguish two forms of measurement: (1) GDP at market prices, which represents the sum of value added (VA) plus taxes net of subsidies on products. (2) GDP at basic prices excludes taxes on products and includes subsidies. Subsequently, we present the changes in wealth produced at the level of each of the economic sectors through the sum of the VA relative to the branches of activity that belong to them.

Without an increase in public spending, the simulation of an increase in inequality in the short term (SIM1) generates a decrease of (-0.24%) in GDP at market prices and (-0.26%) in GDP at basic prices.

At the level of value added, we note a divergence in the sensitivity of each sector to this shock: a decrease in the primary sector of (-0.29%), a growth in industries of 0.2% and a quasi-stagnation in services (+0.01%). Indeed, this increase in inequalities simulated in SIM1 is accompanied by an increase in inequalities in labour income (YHL) of (+17.4%) and capital income (YHK) of (+6.45%) in the Gini sense. These results show that a rise in wage inequality causes a reduction in national GDP. This reduction is associated with the decline in primary sector output. Despite the increase in the VA of the industrial branches and public services, this loss of value added in the primary sector, composed of agriculture and fishing, causes not only a decrease in the income of all categories of households, but also in the private funds of firms illustrated by the FIRM agent, which loses (-0.32%) of its income.

Figure 26 : Impact on national and sectoral production in SIM1

VA public services sector	0,18%
VA private services sector	0,01%
VA industries sector	0,20%
VA agriculture sector	-0,29%
PIB market price	-0,24%
PIB base price	-0,26%

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

Through increased government intervention through current spending, output growth is higher. Indeed, the results of the last four simulations show both an increase in economic performance accompanied by an increase in household and business income, with more reduction in the overall income inequality. SIM6 and SIM4 produce the highest variation in output with a rate of (+4.07%) for GDP at basic prices, a rate of (+3.54%) for GDP at market prices, also an increase of (+5.28%) in primary value added. Under these same simulations, the two sectors, secondary and tertiary excluding the public sector, recorded a counter-performance estimated at an average of more than 3.5 points for industry and a quasi-stagnation for services.

The main variation generated by the shock of SIM1 is the increase in the value added of the "Construction and Public Works" branch (+2.38%). This result is explained in part by the reduction in prices associated

with production costs compared to sales prices (with an index of 0.754). This index means that the cost of production has fallen by more than a quarter of the selling price, which leads to an increase in the value added in this sector. In addition to this industry, we note that activities that experienced deflation in production prices, as well as sales prices, also recorded an increase in value due to SIM1, with (+0.32%) of other industries (AIND) and (+0.66%) of mechanical, metallurgical, and electrical industries (MMI). SIM1 generates a generalized deflation on all branches, whether on sales prices or production costs, especially for production in the secondary industrial and tertiary services sectors. This explains the increase in industrial value added and the stagnation in the service sector.

Figure 27 : Impact of the simulations on value added by industry in SIM1

Source: Model outputs (Chtouki & Raouf, 2023)

On SIM1, the branches that recorded a decline in their value added are firstly other non-financial services (OPO), with a negative variation of (-1.91%), then food and tobacco (IAT) by (-1.05%), electricity and water (PEE) by (-1.03%), marine fishing and aquaculture (PAQ) by (-0.73%), hotels and restaurants (HTR) by (-0.49%), etc. When comparing sales prices to production costs, these industries show a sales price/production cost variation index greater than 1, with the variation in sales prices remaining higher than that of costs. This has the effect of minimizing the profits generated by these activities, explaining therefore the reduction in their contribution to total value added. Through these results, we can see that the performance of industries which production is intended for the larger demand, such as food and household services, declines as income inequality increases. Although, this same unequal environment is favorable to industries in need of strong investment, such as construction or

capital goods maintenance. This is reinforced by the 2.35% increase in GFCF in SIM1.

VI- Analysis and discussion

To summarize the results of the model, we provide an illustration of the socio-economic impact of income inequality using an extrapolation approach of an increase in inequality of 1% in the Gini index (Annex D). As shown in annex, we retain the three simulations outcomes, namely SIM1, SIM3 and SIM6. So, we note that an additional 1% in inequality limits not only the growth potential of poor households but also that of the richest. Encouraging these better-off households to lower their consumption and saving behaviour by more than 10%. An unequal environment is likely to disengage them from participating in the consumption and savings process.

Although it has a reducing effect on inflation, this decline in consumption affects the internal and external commodity markets. In addition to the negative effects on exports (-22.93%), we note that it has a negative impact on firms' private resources, where an increase of 1% leads to a decrease of (-2.23%). This has the effect of reducing the demand for production factors, mainly labour. As long as industrial emergence is not accompanied by an absorption of unemployment, this favorable

economic impact on the industrial secondary sector is accompanied by a negative social impact relating to underemployment. Also, it is important to point out that any leveraging effect associated with investment and the budget surplus is not necessarily linked to inequalities, but rather to the fiscal policy used to check the model.

On the social impact of a 1% increase in income inequality, we detect a decline of more than 2.5% in the income of poor households as well as rural households, since this reduction is associated with a decline of more than 5% in transfers destined to these households. In addition, we notice other factors of this reduction in income that are associated with the reduction in the demand for labour by (-3.13%) and the wage rate by (-1.57%). We also note a considerable decrease in household access to basic commodities (food, education, health and public). However, poor households show a small increase in their ability to access these products. This minor increase is due to the increase in consumption by poor urban households.

Regarding the theoretical implications that justify the results obtained from the model, the following table represents an interpretation of the set of economic and social impact determinants in relation to the theoretical contributions rooted in the economic literature.

Table 2 : Analysis of the socio-economic impact of income inequality

IMPACT DETERMINANTS		EFFECT	ANALYZE & DISCUSSIONS	
IMPACT ECONOMIQUE	Production & economic growth	GDP	Negative	Increasing inequality affects demand in markets of goods and services which in turn affects the profitability of firms and the returns on investment for the richest and encourages rent-seeking (Rodrik, 1999; Nissanke & Thorbecke, 2006) resulting in sluggish growth and an inability to absorb unemployment and increase household incomes. Inequality imposes a cost on the economy (Stiglitz, 2015).
		Primary sector value added (Agriculture & fishing)	Negative	As with industrial food production and financial services, the unequal environment appears to be incompatible with agricultural and fisheries production, where their value-added falls by an average of 0.6 points for every 1% increase in inequality. This is related to the decline in consumption of the basket of basic household products to the detriment of equipment and investment products, especially by non-poor urban households.
		Secondary value added (Industries)	Positive	Income inequality increases the added value of the branches where the activity is based on industrial investment for two reasons: (i) The selling prices of these branches decrease more than the investment costs, generating economies of scale; (ii) the demand for industrial products increases as a substitute for products of a consumable nature, such as industrial food, agricultural and fishing products, etc.
		Tertiary value added (Services)	Mix	Inequality has, on average, little impact on the service sector. However, the construction and real estate branches, which are support services for the realization of durable physical assets, see their demand increase considerably with the rise in inequality. On the other hand, rising inequality affects the performance of the financial sectors by (-1.3%) in terms of average value added.

IMPACT SOCIAL		Firms' revenue	Negative	Declining returns on capital and profits on sales lead to lower returns for companies.
	Labour market	Employment rate	Negative	The relationship between inequality and employment is marked by reciprocity. On the one hand, the rise in unemployment causes a growth in inequality (Tregenna, 2011). This growth in inequality impacts the demand for labour inputs, which leads to underemployment (Acemoglu, 1999).
		Wage rate	Negative	The decline in job demand results in a lower wage rate. This decline in wages is of little benefit to firms (because of their declining revenues).
	Financial market	Return on capital	Negative	The decline in demand for capital is relatively less extreme than that of labour. Consequently, this decline is associated with the decline in economic activity, especially financial.
		Investment rate	Positive	Inequalities have a positive effect on investment (Barro, 2000). However, the excessive rise in physical investment expenditures is accompanied by a limitation in human capital investment (Nissanke and Thorbecke, 2006). This weakens the share of income going to the middle class and reduces demand in the market of commodities.
		National savings/GDP	Negative	Contrary to Kaldor assumption (1957), rising inequality lowers national savings because of the generalized decline in resources in the economy.
	Trade openness	Exportation	Negative	For some (Colluch & al, 2001; Krugman, 2007; Daumal, 2013), trade openness is positively correlated with a decline in inequality, as a redistributive factor. In the case of an increase in income disparities, the factors of production are weakened, even weakening production for export, and reducing external trade.
		Importation	Negative	
	Well-being (Happiness)	Household consumption/GDP	Negative (Extreme)	More inequality presents itself as a decrease in household income, with a deeper rhythm at the low-income level. In this respect, this decrease in resources causes a decrease in consumption, leading to a feeling of unease among individuals belonging to this household (Alesina & al, 2004; Dynan and Ravina, 2007).
		Access to the food product	Negative	Decrease in the consumption of basic household products leads to a feeling of intense unhappiness that affects the well-being.
		Accessibility of poor households to commodities	Positive (weak)	Despite the general decline in household consumption, the small increase in consumption by poor households is due to consumer price deflation, especially in urban region. This causes a slight increase in demand through the price effect.
		Transfers to the poor and rural household	Negative	Theoretically, households that receive additional income tend to invest more in their children's education (Akee & al., 2010). The 5-point drop in transfers following a 1-point increase in inequality has an atrocious effect on households that is not limited to education.
	Education and health	Access of poor household to Social Services	Negative	Economic impact generated by increases of income inequality limits access to social services, affecting human capital (Perotti, 1996; Aghion & al, 1999) which weighs on government spending and economic growth.
		Access of poor household to administrative services	Negative	The more egalitarian the society, the more public policies are oriented towards investment in human capital and social services (Perotti, 1994). This improves the quality and compatibility of public services for households.
		Government budget	Positive	In theory, an increase in the state budget means a possible increase in the budget for social policies, especially when an increase in inequality forces a correction of the redistribution function (Meltzer and Richard, 1981). However, it is important that the increase in inequality is not the origin of this increase in public funds, but rather an effect produced by the overtaxation of rich households. In this respect, the budget surplus only has a social effect when a stimulus policy is implemented.

Source : Author

Conclusion

Even though the world is richer than it used to be, this enrichment is far from reaching everyone (WID, 2018). Beyond its status as the tenth SDG, reducing inequality will have an economic, social and even societal impact on a maintaining a sustainable development in a modern society. For instance, in Morocco, the impact of income inequality must be central to the formulation of any governance policy required to better manage its economy. Thereupon, the conclusion of the thesis includes the main implications, the research hypothesis evaluation, limitations and perspectives of this study.

Main implications

As a general conclusion, we shall highlight the research theoretical and empirical contributions:

- Income distribution is a crucial component in the governance of a modern society. Although conventional modes are well thought out, a redesign of fiscal and tax policies must consider the level of the gap between social classes in order to maintain a harmonious mix without detrimental effects on economic performance, social cohesion and societal balance.
- Inequalities are multidimensional and interactive. However, the monetary or economic form of these inequalities remains a concrete basis for the appreciation of the multiple effects related to the lagged growth of income in a society.
- Throughout economic thought, inequality has played a significant role in the theoretical statements of each of these currents. The literature review developed for our topic shows the mutuality of impact that exists between this phenomenon and its economic and social determinants. In theory, the expansion of inequality is an emerging source of sinister externalities for economic development and the preservation of cohesion.
- Since independence, Morocco has gone through several phases in the evolution of the "Poverty-Growth-Inequality" triangle (PCI), resulting in a set of social programs that are rather aimed at absorbing absolute poverty. As a result, social inequalities remain problematic, even exceeding the critical 40% Gini mark in 2007. However, the assessment of income inequality states that it remains less intense than in neighboring countries (the MENA region) and in the most unequal countries (Brazil, South Africa and the Gulf States). Comparing Morocco to a panel of almost similar economies from 2015, it ranks as more unequal than Egypt, Jordan and Tunisia. While it remains less unequal than Malaysia, Argentina, Turkey and the Philippines. On the other hand, it remains the worst performer on the index of equal access to education, at 55.5% in the Gini sense of education.
- Income inequality in Morocco is characterized by a spatial aspect that distinguishes the income of rural and urban households. This dichotomy is due to the failure of social factors for rural households (e.g. 93.3% of rural households have no family member with medical coverage, compared to 66.1% of urban households), (For example, 93.3% of rural households have no family member with medical coverage, compared to 66.1% of urban households), decadence of their living standards (71% of rural households live in precarious or unhealthy housing) and increased vulnerability to economic shocks (during the confinement imposed during the Covid-19 health crisis, the poverty and vulnerability rates in rural areas reached 57% and 64.4% respectively, compared to 12.7% and 21.5% in urban areas).
- Through CGE modelling, we reject Kuznets' optimistic statements on the relationship between inequality and growth, such that income inequality is a brake on growth even in the short run. Thus, increasing income inequality leads to a less efficient equilibrium in terms of production, consumption and savings and to a more deficient accessibility of poor households to social and public services
- By extension of the model results, (+1%) increase in income inequality decreases Moroccan GDP by (-1.73%) on basic price and (-1.60%) at market price (see annex for more details on the impact of 1% on the general equilibrium).

- By way of possible proposals, we note, through the results of the simulations carried out in the model, that the integration of a negative overtaxation of poor households accompanied by a fiscal stimulus makes it possible to alleviate the harmful effects produced by income inequalities. However, this fiscal and tax policy generates significant inflation which is mainly reflected in the consumer price index. In this respect, we would like to point out that a policy approach to reduce inequality must contain a monetary policy to control inflation.

Research hypothesis evaluation

According to the results of the CGEM, **hypotheses 1, 3 and 4 are rejected**. The increase in income inequality has a negative impact on production as a whole, particularly in the agricultural and fisheries sector. This results from the decrease in consumption of final products caused by the regression of the resources of all households. The negative impact of inequality on economic variables also includes a fall in household savings, a fall in corporate profits and a negative rate of return on factors of production (labour and capital). It is only those industries that are industrial in nature and produce material assets that thrive in the midst of this unequal environment.

Hypothesis 2 is accepted. The negative socio-economic impact is confirmed, both by the simulation scenarios and by the study of the dynamics of inequalities in Morocco. Due to the mutuality of impact between inequalities and their determinants, any damage to distributive justice generates a kind of twin deficit among these inequalities and its causes and consequences.

Research limits

According to academic custom, the limitation of social science studies that include an empirical approach is constantly related to the reliability of the data sources as well as the omnipotence of the modelling results. Due to its cross-cutting nature, the debate on social inequalities and their socio-economic impact presents a generously rich literature review (see the long version). However, its empirical basis remains less enriching. As long as the main, or sometimes only, source of information related to income distribution is household surveys, the reliability of the results is relative. Because statistics from tax sources usually include only the households of the non-poor (those with taxable income),

household surveys are the only ones that provide detailed individualized data on income and expenditure that cover the whole social hierarchy, from the very poor to the very rich. These surveys select a random sample and ask a number of questions on demographics, place of residence, sources and amounts of income and consumption, income from self-employment or asset ownership, etc.

As for the modelling, there are two main limitations to our approach. Firstly, as long as the CGE model used is static, the impact can only be simulated in the short term. Beyond one year, the effects of inequalities can only be appreciated from the exploratory phase. On the other hand, the CGE model does not include mechanisms to study the contributions of monetary policy. Thus, the study does not allow for the simulation of the mitigation of the inflationary effects of the fiscal and budgetary reform via an adequate monetary policy.

Next steps

The possible follow-up to this study consist of a set of research avenues that can further deepen the analysis of this subject. In response to the limitations mentioned above, we consider that a study, particularly an empirical one, is necessary to allow both a simulation of the impact of inequalities in the long term and the incorporation of monetary policy instruments in the specification of the model. This study could be the subject of long-run econometric modelling, such as cointegration models or other macro-dynamic models (such as the ARDL model).

As regards the prospects of studies under the CGE model, we believe that a possible matrix should increase its dimensions. In this respect, the model could contain more disaggregation at the household level, in order to broaden the distribution of income (e.g. repair by quartile of each residence or by decile). Under the same logic, this disaggregation can also be administered to the factors of production, so that they are broken down into skilled and unskilled labour, physical capital (machinery and capital goods), financial capital and other forms of fixed assets (e.g. agricultural land). For the purposes of research, other industries need to be distributed, namely: education, health and social work, and public services (commercial and industrial public administration and social welfare administration).

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ANNEX

A. DESIGNATION OF SECTORS, BRANCHES AND PRODUCTS ON THE MODEL

Sector	Code	Branche	Product	Designation
Primary sector (Agriculture & fishing)	A00	AGR	AGRP	Agriculture, forestry, and related services
	B05	PAQ	PAQP	Fishing, aquaculture
Secondary sector (Industries & manufacturing)	C00	IEX	IEXP	Extraction industry
	D01	IAT	IATP	Food and tobacco industries
	D02	ITC	ITCP	Textile and leather industries
	D03	ICP	ICPP	Chemical and Para-chemical industries
	D04	IMM	IMMP	Mechanical, metallurgical, and electrical industries
	D05	AIND	AINDP	Other industries
Tertiary sector (Services)	E00	PEE	PEEP	Electricity and water
	F45	CST	CSTP	Construction and public works
	G00	COM	COMP	Commerce
	H55	HTR	HTRP	Hotels and restaurants
	I01	TRA	TRAP	Transport
	I02	PTC	PTCP	Post and telecommunications
	J00	AFA	AFAP	Financial and insurance activities
	K00	IML	IMLP	Real estate, renting and business services
	L75	ADM	ADMP	General public administration
	MN0	MNO	MNOP	Education, health and social work
	OP0	OPO	OPOP	Other non-financial services
UFO	TRO		Territorial correction	

B. SOCIAL STRUCTURE & HOUSEHOLD BEHAVIOR

Table B : Main indicators on economic agents in basic equilibrium

	Designation	Income	Consumption	Saving	Population
RPH	Rural Poor household	14065,27	11704,49679	2077,78	14%
UPH	Urban Poor household	18616,47	8428,878059	8751,19	8%
RNPH	Rural Non-Poor household	226421,71	155502,6003	26650,03	35%
UNPH	Urban Non-Poor household	557864,53	413015,0249	63919,27	44%
FIRM	Economic structure (Firms)	302378,73	1143361,042	165908,7673	
GOV	Government	313755,82	311669,8678	33113,98684	
ROW	Rest of the world	491003,3	713932,192	44186	

C. RESULTS OF THE EFFECT OF A RISE ON 1% ON MODEL VARIABLES

Table C: Impact of inequalities on household living standards

	Impact of +1% of income inequality by fiscal policy (SIM1)	Impact of +1% of income inequality by mix policy (SIM3)	Impact of +1% income inequality within policy (SIM6)
Impact on household income (YH)			
RPH	-1,89%	2,97%	2,74%
UPH	-3,03%	1,60%	1,87%
RNPH	-2,54%	3,88%	3,61%
	-2,29%	2,21%	2,21%

UNPH	-1,69%	3,28%	2,96%
Impact on consumption income (YH)	-3,07%	0,71%	1,29%
RPH	-1,07%	-0,11%	0,18%
UPH	4,12%	2,71%	1,88%
RNPH	-2,09%	0,30%	0,63%
UNPH	-13,22%	-0,04%	2,46%
Impact on saving income (YH)	-0,80%	0,56%	0,62%
RPH	-2,47%	1,67%	1,87%
UPH	2,53%	4,50%	3,61%
RNPH	-3,40%	2,07%	2,32%
UNPH	-14,27%	1,77%	4,18%

Table D.2: Economic impact of 1% of income inequality in CGEM

	Impact of +1% of income inequality by fiscal policy (SIM1)	Impact of +1% of income inequality by mix policy (SIM3)	Impact of +1% income inequality within optimal policy (SIM6)
National and sectoral production			
GDP at basic prices	-1,73%	2,72%	2,51%
GDP at market prices	-1,60%	2,35%	2,19%
Value added by sector			
Primary (Agriculture and fisheries)	-1,93%	3,62%	3,26%
Secondary (Industry)	1,33%	-2,76%	-2,46%
Tertiary (Services)	0,07%	-0,03%	-0,04%
including public services (ADM)	1,20%	9,69%	7,53%
Consumption & investment			
Household final consumption/GDP	-9,37%	-0,45%	1,40%
Consumer price index	-1,42%	1,58%	1,53%
National household savings/GDP	-4,18%	-0,15%	0,70%
Investment rate (GFCF/GDP)	17,33%	-7,50%	-9,24%
Investment price index	-0,74%	1,09%	1,01%
Capital demand	-0,02%	-0,06%	-0,04%
of which non-public	-0,02%	-0,06%	-0,05%
Rate of return on capital	-1,81%	1,12%	1,25%
Public and private institutions			
Government budget (YG)	18,03%	3,53%	-0,70%
Price index of public expenditure	-1,53%	4,15%	3,62%
Government transfers to households	-1,42%	1,58%	1,53%
Revenue from taxes on products and imports	-0,35%	-0,41%	-0,27%
of which indirect taxes on consumption	-0,10%	-0,48%	-0,37%
Private funds of enterprises (YFIRM)	-2,35%	1,19%	1,40%
Corporate tax revenue	-1,81%	1,12%	1,25%
Trade openness			
Exports of goods and services	-22,93%	-5,02%	-4,30%
Imports of goods and services	-6,00%	-3,12%	-2,79%

Table D.3: Social impact of 1% of income inequality in CGEM

	Impact of +1% of income inequality by fiscal policy (SIM1)	Impact of +1% of income inequality by mix policy (SIM3)	Impact of +1% income inequality within optimal policy (SIM6)
Standard of living of poor households			
Income of poor households	-2,79%	2,74%	2,74%
Consumption of poor households	1,52%	1,30%	1,03%
Savings of poor households	0,03%	3,09%	2,74%
Transfers to poor households	-5,13%	1,75%	2,39%
Standard of living of rural households			
Rural household income	-2,66%	1,91%	2,04%
Rural household consumption	-1,58%	0,09%	0,41%
Savings of rural households	-2,94%	1,87%	2,10%
Transfer to rural households	-5,01%	1,64%	2,28%
Access to the labour market			
Need for recruitment (demand for labour)	-3,13%	0,13%	0,70%
of which non-public	-3,13%	-0,33%	0,33%
Labour compensation rate (Wages)	-1,57%	5,55%	4,76%
Market access for goods and services			
Access to agricultural and industrial food products	-2,52%	0,52%	1,01%
of which poor households	0,57%	0,39%	0,31%
Access to education, health, and social services	-3,07%	-0,88%	-0,01%
of which poor households	0,54%	-0,29%	-0,22%
Access to government services	-3,07%	-0,84%	0,02%
of which poor households	0,54%	-0,27%	-0,20%